

Soothing touch: Formulation and analysis of a rejuvenating herbal massage cream

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Abstract

The study is all about making a herbal massage cream by using herbal ingredients like dragon fruit, cucumber, black grape strawberry, papaya a newest herbal remedy, to see if it can actually help get rid of those different type skin problem and which is free from side effects and give multipurpose effect, like moisturizer, reduce acne and skin irritation, reduce skin diseases like eczema, psoriasis, dry skin, wrinkles, rashes etc. and also adding glow to the face. Dragon fruit, Cucumber, Black grapes, Strawberry, Papaya, was utilized as the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) in the formulation of an herbal massage cream, alongside complementary base ingredients. The cream formulation was prepared using standardized procedures, incorporating various fruit powder at optimized concentrations and blending it with other constituents to ensure efficacy and safety. The formulated herbal massage cream was shown effective result as a moisturize the skin, hydrate the skin, reduce the sign of aging, and also give a beneficial effect on human skin. The cream was passed through the various evaluation parameters as an effective herbal product. This study supports the feasibility and potential of this herbal formulation as a safe and natural remedy for managing different skin conditions, providing a promising avenue for further research and development in the field of herbal skincare products.

Keyword: Herbal cream; Massage cream; Anti-oxidant; Mix fruit cream

1. Introduction

The present research, researcher formulate an herbal massage cream, which is made by mix up of different fruits like - dragon fruit, cucumber, papaya, strawberry, black grapes for their different properties which play important role in making a herbal massage cream that is shown in table.1. The researcher making herbal massage cream by using a different ingredient (stearic acid, cetyl alcohol, borax, glycerol, olive oil, rose water, methyl paraben) in different quantities which are also mention in the table. 2

Herbal cosmetic is derived from plants and contain natural ingredients believed to have medicinal or therapeutic properties. these products range from teas and supplements to skincare and hair care items, harnessing the power of nature for health and wellness purposes. Herbal cosmetics are beauty products formulated with natural ingredients derived from plants, herbs, flowers, and other botanical sources. These cosmetics often avoid synthetic chemicals and instead rely on the beneficial properties of herbs and plants for skincare and beauty benefits.[1]

1.1. Poly Herbal

Polyherbal formulations involve combining multiple herbs or plant extracts to create a single product with enhanced therapeutic or cosmetic benefits. These formulations have been used for centuries in traditional medicine systems such as Ayurveda, Traditional Chinese Medicine, and Unani. By blending different herbs, polyherbal formulations can target multiple health concerns or provide a broader spectrum of active compounds, leading to synergistic effects. In the context of herbal cosmetics, polyherbal formulations may offer a comprehensive approach to skincare, addressing

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various skin issues simultaneously. These formulations often capitalize on the diverse properties of different herbs, such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, moisturizing, and anti-aging effects, to promote overall skin health and beauty.[2]

1.2. Herbal Cream

Creams are the semisolid formulation apply directly on to the skin. Herbal creams are skincare products formulated with a base of natural ingredients derived from plants, such as herbs, botanical extracts, essential oils, and plant-based oils and butters. These creams are designed to nourish, moisturize, and protect the skin using the beneficial properties of botanical ingredients. Herbal creams may contain a single herb or a combination of herbs known for their skincare benefits, depending on the specific formulation. They are often preferred by those seeking a more natural and gentle approach to skincare, as they typically avoid synthetic chemicals, fragrances, and harsh additives. Herbal creams can be used to address various skin concerns, including dryness, irritation, inflammation, aging, and uneven skin tone, providing hydration, soothing relief, and promoting overall skin health.[3]

1.3. Benefits of Massage Cream

- Provides deep hydration: The massage cream body is formulated with hydrating ingredients that penetrate deep into the skin, providing intense moisture and hydration. This deep hydration can help in rejuvenating rough and dry skin, resulting in soft and supple skin.
- Enhances blood circulation: Massage cream body helps improve blood circulation by making it easier for the therapist to glide over the skin. This gliding motion generates heat that helps relax the muscles, leading to improved blood circulation.
- Reduces muscle tension: Massage therapy is a known remedy for muscle tension, and the use of massage cream body can amplify its effects. The cream provides a smooth surface, making it easier for the therapist to work out knots and tense muscles.
- Helps in pain relief: Massage cream body contains analgesic ingredients that help in reducing pain and inflammation.
- Improves flexibility: The use of massage cream body can also help improve flexibility, relieving joint pain.
- Provides a calming effect: The fragrance and texture of massage cream body provide a calming effect, making it an excellent way to reduce stress and provide relaxation.[5]

2. Materials And Methods

2.1. List of Ingredients and Excipients used for the Preparation of Massage Cream and their Role

The plants for the study were selected, procured from market shade dried, powdered coarsely, and extracted with the hydro-alcoholic solution and used for the formulation The plant materials used for the study are.

2.1.1. Raw Material

Active Pharmaceutical Agent (API)

- Dragon fruit (*Selenicereus undatus*) purchase from local market.
- Papaya (*Carica papaya*) purchase from local market.
- Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) purchase from local market.
- Strawberry (*Fragaria*) purchase from local market.
- Black Grapes (*Vitis Vinifera*) purchase from local market.

Excipients

- Steric acid was purchased from S.D fine chem. Pvt Ltd.
- Glycerol was purchased from S.D fine chem. Pvt Ltd.
- Rose Water was purchased from S.D fine chem. Pvt Ltd.
- Cetylc alcohol was purchased from S.D fine chem. Pvt Ltd.
- Methyl paraben was purchased from S.D fine chem. Pvt Ltd.
- Olive oil was purchased from S.D fine chem. Pvt Ltd.

Various Material and Their Role in Herbal Massage Cream Formulation are Listed Below in the Table

Table 1 Material and their role

Sr.no.	Ingredients	Role of ingredients
1.	Dragon fruit	Moisturization
2.	Raw Papaya	Anti-wrinkle activity
3.	Cucumber	Skin nourishment, soothing, cooling effect, anti-inflammatory activity
4.	Straw berry	Great exfoliator
5.	Black grapes	Anti-oxidant
6.	Stearic acid	emulsifying agent
7	Cetyl alcohol	Emulsifier
8.	Olive oil	Antioxidants
9.	Glycerol	Humectant, (moisturizing agent)
10.	Rose water	q.s
11.	Borax	Emulsifying Agent
12.	Methyl Paraben	Preservative

Table 2 Materials and their Composition

Sr.no.	Ingredients	Composition
1.	Dragon fruit	10gm
2.	Raw Papaya	10gm
3.	Strawberry	10gm
4.	Cucumber	10gm
5.	Black grape	10gm
6.	Stearic acid	5gm
7.	Cetyl alcohol	5gm
8.	Olive oil	5ml
9.	Glycerole	10ml
10.	Rose water	q.s.
11.	Borax	10gm
12.	Methyl Paraben	0.01

Table 3 Equipment's

Sr.no.	Equipment's	Role /use
1.	Weighing Balance	For Weighing
2.	Grinder	For Grinding
3.	Tray Dryer	For Drying
4.	Water bath	For Heating
5.	pH meter	For determination of pH

2.1.2. API (Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients)

Dragon Fruit (*Selenicereus undatus*)

- Help in slowing down the process of ageing.
- Help protect your skin from sun damage.
- Reducing the appearance of dark spots and uneven skin tone.[6]

Figure 1 Cutting and weighing Dragon fruit

Papaya (*Carica papaya*) -

- it may act as a moisturiser and make your skin look smoother.
- used as a skin-lightening agent.
- Exfoliating activity.[7]

Figure 2 Cutting and weighing of Papaya

Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* Linn) -

- Keep Pimples and Acne Off your Face.
- Keeps the Skin Healthy and Toned.

- Helps Combat Signs of Premature Aging.
- A Great Source of Hydration.[8]

Figure 3 Cutting and weighing of Cucumber

Straw Berry (*Fragaria x ananassa*) -

- Antioxidants.
- Anti-ageing.
- help keep your skin free from fine lines and wrinkles.
- reduce the appearance of open pores, and prevent acne and blackheads.[9]

Figure 4 Cutting & weighing of Straw Berry

Black Grapes (*Vitis Vinifera*)

- Antioxidants
- May support heart health
- Reducing the appearance of wrinkles
- Antimicrobial agents.[10]

Figure 5 Cutting & weighing of Black Grapes

2.1.3. Ingredients

Stearic acid

- Stearic acid is used to thicken the products and bind the ingredients together.
- Moisturizing.
- Anti-inflammatory.
- It is used to hydrating the skin.[11]

Figure 6 Weighing of stearic Acid

Cetyl alcohol

- Cetyl alcohol helps prevent creams from separating into oil and liquid.
- emulsifier.
- thickening agent.[12]

Figure 7 Weighing of Cetyl Alcohol

Olive Oil

- Provides softness to the skin.
- Emollient.
- Olive oil is currently used in topical applications for the treatment of several skin conditions including dry skin, itch, and inflammation as well as disorders such as rosacea.[13]

Figure 8 Measuring of Olive Oil

Glycerol

- As a humectant.
- Moisturizing agent.
- Reduces Acne.
- keeps Skin Young.
- Protects Skin.[14]

Figure 9 Weighing of Glycerole

Rose water-

- It is used to maintain fragrance
- Rose water is a soothing Agent.
- moisturizing ingredient.
- It also has anti-bacterial property.
- Antiseptic.[15]

Figure 10 Measuring of Rose Water

Borax-

- Emulsifier.
- Moisturizing.
- Buffering agent.
- Preservative.[16]

Figure 11 Weighing of Borax

Methyl Paraben-

- It prevents germ growth.
- It is also an antifungal preservative.
- It help to increase shelf life.[17]

Figure 12 Weighing of Methyl Paraben

2.2. Evaluation Parameters of Herbal Massage Cream: -

2.2.1. Physical evaluation

Formulated herbal cream was further evaluated by using the following physical parameters. Color, Odor, Consistency, and state of the formulation.

Color

The color of the cream was observed by visual examination. The chocolatey color was obtained.

Odor

The odor of cream was found to be characteristics.

Consistency

The formulation was examined by rubbing cream on hand manually. The cream having smooth consistency. Cream did not leave greasy substances on skin surface after application.

State

The state of cream was examined visually. The cream having a semisolid state.

Determination pH

Accurately weighed 1 gm of sample was dissolve in 10ml of water. The pH of the formulation was obtain 6.3.

Spreadability Test:

Cream base should spread easily without too much drag and should not produce greater friction in the rubbing process. Spreadability was calculated using the spreadability apparatus made of wooden board with scale and two glass slides having two pans on both sides mounted on a pulley.

Excess sample was placed between the two glass slides and 100 g weight was placed on the glass slide for 5 min to compress the sample to a uniform thickness. Weight (250 g) was added to the pan. The time in seconds required to separate the two slides was taken as a measure of spreadability.

$$S = m * l/t$$

m – weight tied on upper slide l – length of glass slide

t – time

Washability Test

The product was applied on hand was observed under running water. The formulation of herbal massage cream was easily washable.

Stability testing

Stability testing was carried out for Formula no. 2 by keeping 50 g of cream at 45°C and another 50 g at room temperature. It was checked for any visual disturbances and phase separation from time to time over a period of 1 month.

Non-Irritation test

Cream shows no redness, irritation, oedema, or inflammation during irritation studies. These formulations are safe to use for the skin and the results.

Homogeneity

The Homogeneity of herbal massage cream was found to be Good.

2.3. Image of Evaluation Parameters

2.3.1. Determination of pH

Figure 13 pH meter

2.3.2. Determination of Spreadability

Figure 14 Spreadability test

2.3.3. Washability Test

Figure 15 Washability test

2.3.4. Trial of cream on our skin in 3 days-

Figure 16 Trial of cream on skin for 3 days

3. Results

The present research was the formulation and evaluation of polyherbal cream. The evaluation parameters were coming under results, like the physical evaluation of herbal massage cream, pH of the cream, Spreadability, Washability, non-irritancy test-

3.1. Organoleptic Evaluation

3.1.1. Effect of Massage Cream in Organoleptic evaluation

Table 4 Effect of Massage Cream

Organoleptic evaluation	
State	Semisolid
Color	Dark brown
Odor	Dark brown
Texture	Smooth
Consistency	Good

The Composition of Herbal Massage Cream formulated in the laboratory was found to be compared with various parameters such as appearance, color, odor and consistency, pH, spread ability, washability, irritancy, homogeneity. Thus, the developed formulation can be used as an effective cosmetic formulation for using it to reduce mind stress, relaxing the body muscles and make skin healthy. It can help to alleviate stress, enhance the immune system, reduce inflammation, improve circulation, moisturize and nourish-h the skin, provide pain relief, and promote overall well-being.

3.1.2. Effect of Massage Cream in Various Type of Skin

Table 5 Effect of Massage Cream in Individual Skin

Sr.no.	Type of skin	Effect of cream
1.	Normal skin	Effective
2.	Dry skin	Effective
3.	Oily skin	Effective
4.	Sensitive skin	No reaction
5.	Combination ski	Effective

3.2. Evaluation Parameters

Table 6 Effect of Massage Cream in Individual Evaluation

Effect of Massage Cream in Individual Evaluation		
S. No	Parameters	Observation
1	State	Semisolid
2	Colour	Dark brown
3	Odor	Good
4	Texture	Smooth
5	Consistency	Good
6	pH	6.3
7	Homogeneity	Good
8	Spread ability	10.23(gm.cm/sec).
9	Washability	Easily and readily washable

4. Discussion

The present research researcher mainly focused on the formulation and evaluation of Herbal massage cream using various evaluation parameters. This cream formulation was o/w type of emulsion; hence this formulation was easily washed with normal water after application. The prepared formulation had a good spreadability. Viscosity and pH of the cream was in range. The herbal massage cream was non-greasy in nature and easily removable after application. The formulation was non-irritant and is not harmful to the skin. The prepared cream showed no phase separation while storage, so this cream has a broad scope in future market because there is no side effect, cost effective, made from natural sources. This cream shows various type of skin benefits like- moisturizing, nourishing, reduce pigmentation, produce soothing effect.

5. Conclusion

In this research, the researcher found the herbal massage cream is more effective than other cosmetics formulation, and has a great scope in future market as a herbal products. Herbs are natural products they are free from side effect, they are comparatively safe, eco-friendly and locally available. Traditionally there is lot of herbs used for the ailments related to different seasons. There is a need to promote them to save the human lives. The need for herbal cosmetics has increased in the personal care industry nowadays, and they are widely used in daily life.

The human body's aesthetic beauty is greatly influenced by the presence of strong teeth, glossy hair, and radiant skin. Herbal cosmetics are created by starting with a base of cosmetic components and adding a variety of herbal substances to cure various skin conditions and enhance beauty. The greatest solution for minimizing skin issues including hyper pigmentation, skin wrinkling, skin ageing, rough skin texture, etc. is to use cosmetic items. The market for herbal cosmetics is expanding quickly. Herbal cosmetics provide advantages such as low cost, no side effects, eco-friendly, safe to use, etc. Comparing the near future to synthetic cosmetics, it looks amazing. The herbal cosmetics industry will see great and considerable expansion as a result of proper regulation and standardization of these plant

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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